

COMPARATIVE ECONOMICS OF CONVENTIONAL VS HIGH DENSITY PLANTING SYSTEM OF BT COTTON IN YAVATMAL DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA.

¹AB Botare, ²US Bondar, ³BT Kolgane, ⁴MS Jadhav and ⁵BJ Deshmukh

¹Msc. Scholar, RCSM, COA, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India

²Assistant Professor of Department of Agricultural Economics, COA, Karad, Maharashtra, India

³Associate Professor of Department of Agricultural Extension, RCSM, COA, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India

⁴Associate Professor, Department of Agricultural Economics, COA, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India

⁵Senior Research Assistant, Department of Agricultural Economics, COA, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India

MS Received: 27.06.2025; MS Revised: 28.07.2025; MS Accepted: 29.07.2025)

MS 3439

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS)

Abstract

The present study was undertaken in Yavatmal district of Maharashtra state in which cotton crop is grown as important commercial crop. The investigation was carried out with view to examine the trends in area, production and productivity and comparative resource use structure, to estimate per hectare cost and returns. The study also assessed major constraints faced by farmers practicing high density planting system (HDPS). In cotton cultivation from Yavatmal district of Maharashtra state. The investigation was based on primary data on 45 conventional and 45 HDPS of cotton farmers collected from three tehsil namely Ralegaon, Kalamb and Bahulgaon of Yavatmal district. Pertained to the year 2023-24. Maharashtra's cotton sector experienced substantial increases in area, production, and productivity area remains steady in last decade's 2004-05 to 2023-24 whereas Yavatmal district experienced moderate growth in acreage and notable increases in both production and yield in 2004-05 to 2013-14 due to use Bt cotton varieties but in this district experienced a gradual and statistically significant rise in the area under cotton cultivation. However, despite some improvements, production and productivity showed inconsistent trends with considerable variability, likely influenced by factors such as climatic changes, pest attacks like bollworm, and uneven use of agricultural inputs in 2014-15 to 2023-24. HDPS farmers demonstrated comparatively higher utilization of resources across nearly all inputs than the conventional except nitrogen, phosphorus and potash because conventional farmers had not followed fertiliser use recommendations. Additionally, cotton yield was also greater on HDPS farmers compared to the conventional. The per hectare cost of cultivation of cotton was worked out to be ₹ 160411.80 in HDPS while in Conventional 143067.10. The cost 'A' was ₹ 126043.45 in HDPS and 105793.75 in conventional or contributing 78.57 and 73.95 per cent share in the cost 'C' in HDPS and conventional. In cost 'A', the major item of cost was hired human labour i.e., ₹ 38325.33 and ₹ 49338.78 in conventional and HDPS, contributing 26.79 and 30.76 per cent share in the cost 'C' in conventional and HDPS. The per hectare expenditure on plant protection charges was worked out to ₹ 7100.20 and 12635.51 contributing 4.96 and 7.88 per cent share in the cost 'C' in conventional and HDPS. B:C ratio was 2.09 and 1.48 in HDPS and conventional system. The constraints such as in-appropriate rainfall, unavailability of timely labour in peak period, bollworm complex management, variable market price of cotton and others were the major constraints faced by HDPS cotton farmers, in the cotton production. The study suggested that, the farmer should enhance their existing productivity of 28.30 and 44.70 quintals/ha which is fair below than that of potential productivity 30 and 48 quintal/ha of conventional and HDPS by adopting recommend package of practices in cotton for minimizing the yield gap.

Keywords: Cotton, Conventional, High Density Planting System, Net return, Income, Cost of cultivation.

Introduction

Drawing from previous Agricultural experiences, Indian farmers are increasingly adopting alternative cultivation techniques, with HDPS emerging as a promising method to enhance cotton yields. HDPS is being viewed as a viable alternative to traditional practices, offering advantages such as suitability for mechanical harvesting, lower labour costs, better resource efficiency, and higher productivity and profitability. This method has already gained widespread acceptance in major cotton-producing countries worldwide.

Efficient water management plays a critical role in the success of HDPS, especially in the face of limited freshwater availability. Proper irrigation practices are necessary to regulate excessive vegetative growth and to ensure that nutrients and assimilates are directed toward the plant's reproductive parts. In this regard, deficit irrigation an approach that conserves water while maintaining yield levels has proven to be effective. It involves using less water than conventional evapotranspiration demands, contributing to more sustainable cotton farming.

This review emphasizes the significance of integrating HDPS with deficit irrigation to develop a sustainable cotton production model. By merging the latest research with field-level practices, it provides a theoretical framework to guide the future evolution of cotton cultivation systems. HDPS also involves the targeted use of herbicides such as Quizalofop-ethyl 5 percentage EC and Pyriithiobac-sodium 10 percentage EC for weed control, as well as growth regulators like Mepiquat Chloride and Chlormequat Chloride to manage plant development. In combination with optimized fertilization and

comprehensive pest and insect control measures, HDPS is ushering in a new era in cotton farming.

It is one of the new systems of cultivation of cotton, popularly known as "Ultra Narrow Row" cotton developed in India by the Central Institute of Cotton Research, Nagpur in 2010. This system conceived as an alternate production system having potential for improving yield, profitability, increasing efficiency, reducing input costs and risk minimization associated with the cotton production system.

Methodology

Study Area: Ralegaon, Kalamb and Bahulgaon tahsils, Yavatmal district.

Sample Size: 90 farmers (45 Conventional and 45 High Density Planting System).

Data Collection: Primary data was collected using personal interviews with structured questionnaires during the year 2023-24.

Cost Concepts:

□ *Variable Costs:* Human labour, Bullock power, Machine labour, Seed, Manure, Fertiliser, Plant protection, Irrigation, etc.

□ *Fixed Costs:* Depreciation, interest on capital.

Analytical Tools:

Compound Annual growth rate (CAGR) = $Y = ab^t$

Cobb-Douglas type of production function to determine the resource use structure.

Estimation of Resource Use Efficiency

$$MVP = \left[\mathbf{b} \mathbf{i} \frac{\bar{Y}}{\bar{X}_1} \right] P_y$$

RPI method.
To pertain Objectives
To estimate the growth rate of area ,production and productivity of Bt cotton.
To workout the economic in conventional Vs high density planting system of Bt cotton.

To examine the constraints faced by Bt cotton in high density planting system and suggest suitable measures.

Results and Discussion

The trend regarding growth rate of Area, Production and Productivity of Cotton in Maharashtra and Yavatmal is presented in Table no.1 and 2.

Table no.1 CAGR in Area, Production and Productivity of Cotton in Maharashtra

Period(2004-05 to 2013-14)	Area	Production	Productivity
CGR	5.12 ***	11.17 ***	5.74 **
R2	0.92 ***	0.75 ***	0.47 **
CV	15.81	33.60	23.70
Coppock Index	0.56	4.73	1.98
Cuddy and Della	4.34	16.60	17.25
Period(2014-15 to 2023-24)	Area	Production	Productivity
CGR	0.42 NS	8.62 **	8.17 **
R2	0.18 NS	0.45 **	0.43 **
CV	2.98	32.96	32.60
Coppock Index	0.01	3.23	3.06
Cuddy and Della	2.70	24.37	24.54

Note:*, ** and *** indicates significance at 10, 5 and 1%level of significance, NS Non-significant.

It is concluded that from Table No.1 During 2004–05 and 2013–14, Maharashtra's cotton sector experienced substantial increases in area, production, and productivity. Nevertheless, this progress was marked by considerable annual variations, especially in production and yield, reflecting a degree of instability in the sector's performance. During 2014–15 and 2023–24, Maharashtra witnessed notable growth in cotton production and productivity, whereas the area under cultivation showed little change. However, these advancements were accompanied by significant year-to-year variations in output and yield, reflecting persistent instability in the sector.

The growth rate of Area, Production and Productivity presented in Table No.2 From 2004–05 to 2013–14, cotton cultivation in Yavatmal

experienced moderate growth in acreage and notable increases in both production and yield, possibly resulting from enhanced agricultural practices. However, this advancement was accompanied by significant fluctuations in output and productivity, primarily due to the variability linked with high-density planting methods and use of Bt. cotton varieties .During 2014–15 and 2023–24, Yavatmal experienced a gradual and statistically significant rise in the area under cotton cultivation. However, despite some improvements, production and productivity showed inconsistent trends with considerable variability, likely influenced by factors such as climatic changes, pest attacks like bollworm, and uneven use of agricultural inputs. (Similar trends were obtained by Deshmukh and Kulkarni (2023).

Table No.2 CAGR in Area, Production and Productivity of Cotton in Yavatmal District

Period (2004-05 to 2013-14)	Area	Production	Productivity
CGR	3.57 **	11.2 **	7.37 *
R2	0.58 **	0.503 **	0.383 *
CV	13.58	39.24	33.08
Coppock Index	0.191	3.098	1.739
Cuddy and Della	8.8	27.65	25.97
Period (2014-15 to 2023-24)	Area	Production	Productivity
CGR	1.33 ***	7.56 NS	6.15 NS
R2	0.621 ***	0.287 NS	0.202 NS
CV	4.96	38.45	39.7
Coppock Index	0.045	6.87	5.755

Note:*, ** and *** indicates significance at 10, 5 and 1%level of significance, NS Non-significant.

The cost of cotton cultivation per hectare is presented in Table No.3. For Conventional farmers, the total cost of cultivation was ₹143067.10 per hectare. Within this, Cost 'A' amounted to ₹105793.75 representing 73.95 % of the overall cost (referred to as Cost 'C'). Among the components of Cost 'A', hired human labour was the, totalling ₹38325.33 and accounting for 26.79 % of Cost 'C'. The expenditures on

seed, manures, and fertilizers were ₹4310.28, ₹6782.22, and ₹ 9527.21 per hectare, contributing 3.01%, 4.74%, and 6.66 % to Cost 'C', respectively. Under Cost 'B', the largest expenses were the rental value of land and interest on fixed capital, making up 19.01% and 2.53% of the total cost, respectively.

Figure No.1. (Area Production and Productivity of Bt Cotton in Maharashtra State.)

Figure No.2. (Area Production and Productivity of Bt Cotton in Yavatmal Dist)

Table No.3 Per Hectare Costs and Returns Structure for Cotton

(Per ha)

Sr.no.	Cost items	Conventional			HDPS		
		Qty	Value	Percent	Qty	Value	Percent
1	Hired labour(Days)						
	Male	24.12	7235.33	5.06	20.31	6092.78	3.80
	Female	155.45	31090.00	21.73	216.23	43246.00	26.96
2	Bullock power(Hrs)	11.27	7886.67	5.51	10.76	7528.89	4.69
3	Machine power(Hrs)	11.96	8368.89	5.85	8.99	6295.27	3.92
4	Seed(Kg)	2.49	4310.28	3.01	4.96	8564.06	5.34
5	Manure(Qtls)	16.96	6782.22	4.74	23.47	9386.67	5.85
6	Fertiliser						
	N(Kg)	230.32	2664.81	1.86	125.03	1446.57	0.90
	P(Kg)	159.05	4612.40	3.22	68.78	1994.56	1.24
	K(Kg)	75.00	2250.00	1.57	43.47	1304.13	0.81
	Fertiliser cost		9527.21	6.66		4745.25	2.96
7	Irrigation charges		3500.00	2.45		2477.92	1.54
8	Plant protection charges		7100.20	4.96		12635.51	7.88

9	Herbicide		3653.50	2.55		4500.00	2.81
10	Growth regulator		1659.18	1.16		2219.91	1.38
11	Maintanance		3200.59	2.24		3199.80	1.99
12	Transportation+Miscellaneous		3860.32	2.70		5320.95	3.32
13	Working capital		98174.39	68.62		116213.01	72.45
14	Interest on working capital		5890.46	4.12		6972.78	4.35
15	Depreciation charges		1630.66	1.14		2756.44	1.72
16	Land revenue		98.23	0.07		101.22	0.06
17	Cost(A)		105793.75	73.95		126043.45	78.57
18	Rental value of land		27194.86	19.01		28900.22	18.02
19	Interest on fixed capital		3619.49	2.53		2890.02	1.80
20	Cost(B)		136608.10	95.49		157833.69	98.39
21	Family labour						
	Male	12.33	3699.00	2.59	6.89	2067.00	1.29
	Female	13.80	2760.00	1.93	2.56	511.11	0.32
22	Cost (C)		143067.10	100.00		160411.80	100.00
23	Income	28.30	212250.00		44.70	335250.00	
24	Per quintal cost		5055.37			3588.63	
25	B:C Ratio		1.48			2.09	

Table No.4 Constraints Faced During Production of HDPS Cotton

Problem No.	Problem Description	Total Score	Mean Score Value (MSV)	Response Priority Index (RPI%)	RPI Rank
1	Inappropriate Rainfall	43	0.96	9.56	I
2	Unavailability of timely labour	40	0.89	8.89	II
3	High Weed management cost	26	0.58	5.78	VIII
4	Lack of required training on HDPS	25	0.56	5.56	IX
5	Lodging effect	34	0.76	7.56	V
6	Lack of institutional credit	21	0.47	4.67	X
7	Variable market price of cotton	35	0.78	7.78	IV
8	Bollworm complex management	37	0.82	8.22	III
9	High cost of pest and disease management	31	0.69	6.89	VI
10	High harvesting cost	29	0.64	6.44	VII

For HDPS farmers, the Per hectare cost of cultivation was higher at ₹ 160411.80 . Cost 'A' in this group was ₹126043.45 forming 78.57 % of the total cost. Here, the major component of Cost 'A' was the hired human labour was the, totalling ₹49338.78 and accounting for 30.76% of cost C and plant protection charges, which amounted to ₹12635.51 and represented 7.88% of Cost 'C'. Fertilizer expenses stood at ₹ 4745.25 (2.96 % of Cost 'C'), seed costs were ₹8564.06. Additionally, the machine power usage cost made up 3.92% of the total cost. Within Cost 'B', the rental value of land remained the dominant expense, contributing 18.02 % to the total cost. (Similar findings were obtained by ICAR-CICR (2022).

The data highlights the major constraints faced by farmers practicing High-Density Planting System (HDPS) in cotton cultivation shown in

Table 5.21. The most pressing issue identified is inappropriate rainfall, which received the highest Response Priority Index (RPI) of 9.56%, followed by the unavailability of timely labour (8.89%), and challenges in managing the bollworm complex (8.22%). These top-ranked problems suggest a strong dependency on weather and labour availability, both critical for the success of HDPS. Price fluctuations in the cotton market and lodging effects were also notable concerns, with RPI values of 7.78% and 7.56%, respectively. Issues like high pest and disease management costs, and harvesting expenses were moderately significant. On the lower end, lack of training and institutional credit access received the least priority, indicating that while they are problems, farmers may perceive them as less immediate or impactful compared to other constraints. (it

was observed that same result obtained by Sharma, A., and Deshmukh, R. (2023).

Conclusion and policy implications

The study revealed that, HDPS practice is profitable as compare to the conventional most of the farmers are unaware about CICR recommended technologies for cotton crop, therefore there is need to disseminate the technology through extension workers of the state to increase the cotton productivity. The study conclude that there is existence of high wages and labour scarcity problems so it can be overcomes by provision of subsidies machines and implements like cotton picking implements because cotton harvesting is most expensive operation. Promotion of high density planting system among the farmers because it has more potential to increase benefit of farmers as compared to the conventional method.

References

1. Acharya, S., Patil, S. L., and Rao, D. R. (2011). Growth trends in area, production and productivity of major crops in Karnataka. *Agricultural Economics Research Review*, 24(2), pp 289–297.
2. Ananthi, M. (2000). Growth of area, production, productivity and export of Indian non-basmati and basmati rice (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore.
3. Anonymous ICAR-CICR, (2022) Indian Council of Agricultural Research – Central Institute for Cotton Research. Retrieved from <https://cicr.org.in>
4. Balamurugan, M., and Ramesh, T. (2022). Constraints in adoption of HDPS cotton technology among smallholders in Tamil Nadu. *Indian Journal of Extension Education*, 58(1), pp 112–117.
5. Bansode, R. R. (2002). Constraints in production and marketing of sorghum in Latur district. *Maharashtra Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 15(2), pp 91–94.

6. Deshmukh, A. R., and Kulkarni, S. P. (2023). Trends in area, production and productivity of Bt. cotton in Vidarbha and Marathwada regions of Maharashtra. *Agricultural Situation in India*, 80(4), pp 45–52.
7. Gohil, H. R., and Patel, J. R. (2021). Constraints faced by cotton growers in adoption of HDPS technology. *Gujarat Agricultural Universities Research Journal*, 46(2), pp 124–128.
8. Jadhav, A. S., and Pawar, M. S. (2023). Economic analysis of Bt. cotton under HDPS and conventional systems in Western Maharashtra. *International Journal of Agriculture Sciences*, 15(1), pp 31–36.
9. Meena, R. S., and Singh, B. (2020). Economic returns under high density and conventional cotton planting systems in Gujarat. *Indian Journal of Extension Education*, 56(4), pp 90–94.
10. Pawar, M. S., and Jadhav, A. S. (2023). Comparative study of resource use and profitability in HDPS and conventional Bt. cotton farms. *Maharashtra Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 26(1), pp 72–78. Sam, K., Kumaraswamy, D., Vijaya Kumari, R., and Supriya, K. (2021). Economic performance of High Density Planting System (HDPS) in cotton: Evidence from Telangana. *Indian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 76(3), pp 301–308.
11. Satpute, T. G., Gabhane, V. V., and Kadam, R. P. (2009). Comparative economics of cotton production under organic and inorganic farming in Parbhani district. *PKV Research Journal*, 33(2), pp 150–153.
12. Sharma, A., and Deshmukh, R. (2023). Constraints in high-density planting system (HDPS) of cotton: Evidence from Vidarbha. *Journal of Cotton Research and Development*, 37(1), pp 45–52.